

Synthesis of complexes of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II), manganese(II) and iron(III) with bidentate Schiff bases

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The complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} with some Schiff bases derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-2H-pyran-2,4(3H)-dione (dehydroacetic acid; DHA) with *p*-toluidine, *p*-bromoaniline and *p*-anisidine have been synthesized. The stoichiometry of the complexes has been found to be 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. The Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} complexes are monomeric with high-spin octahedral geometry, while the Mn^{II} complexes are dimeric in nature. Various ligand field parameters have been calculated. The fungicidal activities of the complexes have been screened.

We report herein the synthesis and characterization of some bidentate Schiff bases (I) derived from biologically active dehydroacetic acid and *p*-toluidine (L₁), *p*-bromoaniline (L₂) and *p*-anisidine (L₃).

Results and Discussion

All the chelates (Table 1) are coloured solids, stable to air and non-hygroscopic. They are insoluble in water but

soluble in DMF, DMSO and other organic solvents. The molar conductance values of all the complexes in DMSO at a concentration of 10⁻⁴ M are very low (5–30 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹), indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The analytical data indicate 1 : 2 metal : ligand stoichiometry for the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} complexes and 1 : 1 stoichiometry for the Mn^{II} complexes.

The disappearance of IR band at 2600 cm⁻¹ (intramolecular hydrogen bonding) in the spectra of all the complexes, indicates deprotonation of enolic group on complex formation. The participation of enolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen in coordination to the metal ion is further supported by an upward shift in ν_{C=O} by 20–30 cm⁻¹ and a downward shift in ν_{C=N} by 15–20 cm⁻¹ in all the com-

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Compd.*	Mol. wt.	Decomp. temp., °C	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	μ _{eff} B.M.	Dq ₁ cm ⁻¹	B cm ⁻¹	β	ν ₂ /ν ₁	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
Cu ^{II} -L ₁	577	280	10.98 (11.00)	1.61	1190	—	—	—	33.92
Cu ^{II} -L ₂	707	280	8.96 (8.98)	1.71	1219	—	—	—	34.75
Cu ^{II} -L ₃	609	240	10.41 (10.42)	1.83	1176	—	—	—	33.52
Ni ^{II} -L ₁	572	>280	10.22 (10.24)	3.01	1063	675	0.65	1.44	30.31
Ni ^{II} -L ₂	702	>280	8.33 (8.35)	3.16	1050	746	0.72	1.56	29.83
Ni ^{II} -L ₃	604	>280	9.68 (9.70)	3.00	1041	720	0.69	1.47	29.58
Co ^{II} -L ₁	572	>290	10.29 (10.30)	5.19	1030	9.57	0.98	1.79	29.38
Co ^{II} -L ₂	702	>290	8.37 (8.39)	4.90	1020	848	0.87	1.63	29.08
Co ^{II} -L ₃	604	>290	9.73 (9.75)	4.93	10.39	898	0.92	1.81	29.61
Fe ^{III} -L ₁	605	270	9.21 (9.23)	4.98	—	—	—	—	—
Fe ^{III} -L ₂	735	225	7.58 (7.59)	4.97	—	—	—	—	—
Fe ^{III} -L ₃	637	250	8.75 (8.76)	5.12	—	—	—	—	—
Mn ^{II} -L ₁	568	>280	9.67 (9.67)	5.45	—	—	—	—	—
Mn ^{II} -L ₂	698	>280	7.85 (7.87)	4.73	—	—	—	—	—
Mn ^{II} -L ₃	600	>290	9.14 (9.15)	4.85	—	—	—	—	—

*L₁ = 1-(4-Methylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-(2',4'-dione-6'-methyl-3-pyran)imine, L₂ = 1-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methyl-2-(2',4'-dione-6'-methyl-3-pyran)imine, L₃ = 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyl-2-(2',4'-dione-6'-methyl-3-pyran)imine.

plexes¹. The strong evidence of bonding is revealed by the appearance of bands at 410–480 (M–N) and 480–530 cm⁻¹ (M–O) in the spectra of the complexes².

The magnetic moment values (Table 1) provide evidence for octahedral geometry for all the complexes. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed a band at 15384–16260 cm⁻¹ assignable to the transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ which is characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry. This is further supported by the magnetic moment values (1.61–1.83 B.M.) within the required range for d^9 -systems³. The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes showed three bands at 10416–10638 (ν_1), 15384–16393 (ν_2) and 26315–26666 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) assigned to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, in an octahedral geometry around the metal ion⁴. The magnetic moment values (3.01–3.16 B.M.) also support the above structure. The Co^{II} complexes exhibited bands at 10204–10390 (ν_1), 16666–18867 (ν_2) and 25777–26777 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) which may be attributed to three spin-allowed transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry⁵. The effective magnetic moment values (4.93–5.19 B.M.) were found to be well within the range as expected for octahedral Co^{II} complexes⁶. The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complexes exhibited three bands at 17241–17543, 23255–23809 and at 26315 cm⁻¹ assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively, indicating tetrahedral/octahedral geometry⁷. The electronic spectra of the complexes cannot prove alone the tetrahedral or octahedral geometry since Mn(II) has d^5 -electronic configuration, the same type of energy level diagram applies whether the metal ion is surrounded by tetrahedral or octahedral environment⁸. The magnetic moment values (4.73–5.45 B.M.) also support the above structure. The Mn^{II} complexes showed the magnetic moment (4.85–5.45 B.M.) which is slightly lower than the spin-only value expected for tetrahedral Mn^{II} complexes⁹. This may be due to the presence of magnetic exchange and small traces of Mn^{III} species¹⁰. In addition to the metal analysis, this is an additional evidence for the dimeric nature of Mn^{II} complexes¹¹. The subnormal magnetic moment values are indicative of metal-metal interactions supporting dimeric structures¹¹. The Fe^{III} complexes showed bands at 16666, 23529, 29411 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_1(D)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions, respectively¹². The magnetic moment value (4.97–5.12 B.M.) indicates high-spin octahedral geometry¹³.

The values of ligand field parameters are presented in Table 1. The B - and β -values have been calculated only for the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes following standard equations¹⁴.

The B -values are lower than the free-ion values, thereby indicating the orbital overlap and delocalization of d -orbitals. The β -values obtained are less than unity suggesting considerable amount of covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds¹⁵. The ratio of ν_2/ν_1 being less than 2 as required for octahedral complexes, which was further supported the distortion from octahedral geometry by the values of Dq and B^{15} . The LFSE values show that the Cu^{II} complexes are more stabilised than the other complexes.

The nature of the water molecules indicated in the IR spectra were further ascertained by thermal analysis. The wt. losses for Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes encountered within the range 67–87° supported by a broad endothermic peak at the same temperature in DTA curve, corresponding to one molecule of water of crystallization¹⁶. However, the first loss for the Co^{II} complexes that occurred at 110.5° supported by a broad endothermic peak at the same temperature in DTA curve, is the characteristic of lattice water molecule. The DTA thermograms of the binuclear Mn^{II} complexes exhibited the characteristic of water of crystallization. Loss of water of crystallization was observed at 60–90°. The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes did not show any mass-loss up to 260°, indicating absence of lattice water, and the complexes decomposed at 314 and 343°, respectively. All the complexes finally decomposed to their metal oxides.

The Schiff bases and their metal chelates were screened (at 250 and 500 ppm) *in vitro* for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*. The ligands showed 60–70% inhibition. The complexes had greater antifungal activity than the corresponding ligands. The order of inhibition for the complexes is Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Fe^{III} > Mn^{II} > Co^{II}. The results are similar to the observations made by other workers¹⁷. The obtained results are also supported by ANOVA calculations¹⁸. The values obtained by variance ratio (F) at 250 ppm clearly indicate significant variation due to both ligands as well as complexes. However, the value of F for metal complexes was high (73.94) in comparison to that obtained for the ligands (6.30), indicating high response of metal complexes rather than ligands for fungal growth. However, when the fungi (*A. niger*) was cultivated on a concentration at 500 ppm, the ANOVA results indicated highly significant difference due to metal complexes. The difference of variation due to ligands was statistically non-significant. This confirms that the metal complexes are responsible for causing variation in the growth of the fungi.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were purified by distillation before use. C, H and N

were analysed at North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃, TMS internal standard) were recorded at N.C.L., Pune. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 150 spectrophotometer and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 FTIR spectrophotometer. Magnetic moment at room temperature was measured on Gouy's balance using HgCo(CNS)₄ as calibrant. Thermogram was recorded on a STA 409C instrument at R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Chennai.

Preparation of ligands : The ligands, DHA-4-methylphenylanil (L₁), DHA-4-bromophenylanil (L₂) and DHA-4-methoxyphenylanil (L₃) were prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of DHA and the corresponding amine in ethanol and refluxing the mixture for 4 h. After cooling, the product was crystallized from ethanol. The purity of the ligands was checked by m.p., TLC and elemental analysis.

Preparation of complexes : To hot methanolic solution (30 ml) of the Schiff base (2 mmol), methanolic solution (20 ml) of metal chloride (1 mmol) was added dropwise with stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained around 7.5 by adding 10% methanolic solution of ammonia. It was then refluxed for 2 h. The resulting metal complex was filtered in hot condition and washed with hot methanol and ether, and dried over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator.

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